

INDUSTRY – INSTITUTE COLLABORATION : NEED OF THE HOUR

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ABSTRACT

The world today belongs to professionals, whether one is in business, industry, government service or teaching profession. One has to be a professional in one's field to maintain competitiveness and efficiency in his/her area of activity.

For proper coordination between the ongoing research in the educational institutes and the demand of the development in the industrial sector it is very essential that we awake to the necessity of Industry – Institute Collaboration.

The paper emphasis on the necessity and the benefits of Industry – Institute Collaboration.

DISCUSSIONS

The world today belongs to professionals, whether one is in business, industry, government service or teaching profession. One has to be a professional in one's field to maintain competitiveness and efficiency in his/her area of activity.

Research and development is the backbone for the success of any country. This research should be such that it can be implemented on field for the development and benefit of the country and similarly any steps towards development should have a research background. Jointly used, research and development help in further enhancement of the existing knowledge, ideas, processes and skill with a view to achieve enhanced quality in service and product, ensures credibility, economy and time saving and of course boosts profit margins.

The need of the hour is that the industry and educational institutes should bridge the gap and develop a system which would revive both parts on a continuing programme basis with novel ideas.

This task can be achieved by a proper industry – institute collaboration. This paper emphasizes the need for such industry – institute collaboration.

Our past experiences have shown that such industry – institute collaboration or interaction have not only helped in solving major problems but have also helped both the parties in

upgrading their knowledge. The industry and the educational institutes have sort of a mutual dependency on each other. The industry relies on the educational institutes for its basics where as the institutes are made aware of the latest technologies and problems by the industry.

We all know that the first step towards any research is based on the basic knowledge given by the educational institutes. Take any example : -

- The fusion or fission of atoms releases enormous amount of energy which is the base for the development of atom bombs used for destruction.
- Writing programs in Java / C++ may be taught theoretically but it becomes the base for the development of softwares for various purposes.
- The theory of aerodynamics is taught in fluid mechanics but has been put to a practical application by the Wright Brothers by designing an aeroplane.
- That potential energy can be converted to kinetic energy is a theory but it has been used for power generation in various hydropower projects.

All these examples and several others which are not mentioned are the results of the creativity or research of a handful of people. But the need of the hour is different.

Just like we say "Let noble thoughts come from all directions", what we need today is that "Let good ideas come from each and every individual". India is a fast developing country and there are lots of intellectuals in our country, but it is yet a long distance to go to compete with the super powers of the world. Waiting for a few people to carry out research would lead us nowhere. On the other hand, there are so many people who, if given proper exposure, can work miracles for this nation. The need of the hour is that each individual gives his / her own contribution towards development, progress and achievements of this country.

As staff members of Engineering Institutes, if we go on teaching the same syllabus to our students till we retire, we would not only be doing injustice to the students by giving them outdated information but also to ourselves for not upgrading our data and also to the society by giving them inefficient technocrats.

Frequent exposure to the problems faced by the industries and research and consultancy to solve those problems would be a sure shot way to upgrade our information and pass it on to the students. Another way to achieve this is by undertaking various research projects and consultancies based on the practical problems faced by the industries. This would not only bring awareness about the technical problems faced by the industry in putting into application the basic engineering to the staff and the students of the engineering institutes but also help the industry in using the expertise of the teaching professional in solving their problems. Such consultancy would also help the educational institutions to be financially independent to some extent and it would become as if the industry gives its contribution towards its alma mater. Research project or training programmes or consultancies involving the students to some extent would finally result in better and efficient engineers for the future.

With this, let us encourage interaction or collaboration between our educational institutes and the industries for the betterment of our students, for the betterment of our institutions and industries.

Thank you.